

Diel and seasonal patterns of methane fluxes in ricefields

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Methane fluxes in ricefields show distinct diel and seasonal variations (Fig. 1a, b), but controlling factors and processes are poorly understood.

Emissions usually increase rapidly after sunrise, peak in the early afternoon, then decline rapidly and level off at night. Cutting the rice shoot above the water level has no immediate effect on diel emission patterns and amplitudes, indicating that plant metabolism does not directly affect CH₄ flux. The diel amplitude of fluxes correlates with the diel soil

temperature changes. The relationship between temperature and CH₄ flux changes with crop development stage (Fig. 2). At the later growth stage, the slope is steep because of greater partial pressure of CH₄ in the soil, higher root biomass, and increased plant-mediated gas transport and capacity (greater aerenchyma volume and tiller number).

Generally, CH₄ emissions are higher in the dry season than in the wet season. If ricefields are kept flooded during the entire growing season, up to three distinct seasonal maxima are observed (Fig. 1b): the first develops shortly after flooding, the second during the later vegetative period, and the third—being the highest—during the grain-filling and maturity stages. The first peak reflects the initial flux of fermenting easily degradable soil organic matter present after flooding. If the amount of easily degradable soil C is low, no initial peak of CH₄ flux develops. The increasing capacity of plant-mediated CH₄ emission and probably the increase in release of plant-borne C sources cause the increasing peaks. CH₄ production and CH₄ oxidation over the entire cropping season will be quantified in future research to elucidate the net flux of CH₄. ■

1a. Diel variation of CH₄ emission. IRRI, 1992 DS.

1b. Methane emission during two seasons under urea fertilization. IRRI, 1992 DS and WS.

2. Methane emission and air temperature in urea-treated plots. 1992 WS, 1993 DS.

Effect of fertilization on methane emission

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Nitrogen, although crucial in achieving high yields in wetland rice, is the most deficient nutrient in the ecosystem. Most farmers apply N fertilizer in two or three splits as urea or (NH₄)₂SO₄. Part of the fertilizer is incorporated into the soil during the final land preparation stage or broadcast shortly after planting. The remainder is applied at midtillering and at panicle initiation.

The effects of N fertilization on CH₄ production and emission are inconsistent. The complex interrelationships between fertilization and biochemistry of flooded soils, plant growth, and CH₄ fluxes, however, still need to be elucidated.

We evaluated the effects of different N fertilizers and modes of fertilizer